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Evaluation of the Protective Effects of Liquiritigenin against Glycerol-Induced Acute Kidney Injury in Male Rabbits

Abstract

Background: Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a severe condition characterized by rapid kidney function deterioration, often triggered by oxidative stress and inflammation. Glycerol-induced AKI is a well-established experimental model that mimics myoglobinuria-associated renal injury.

Objective: This study aims to evaluate the protective effects of the flavonoid liquiritigenin (LQ) against glycerol (GLY)-induced myoglobinuria, a model of acute kidney injury (AKI) in rabbits, focusing on its potential to reduce renal damage via antioxidant and anti-inflammatory mechanisms.

Materials and Methods: Sixty male albino rabbits were divided into five groups: control, induction group (AKI group), vehicle group, and two treatment groups receiving LQ at 30 mg/kg and 50 mg/kg. GLY-induced AKI was established by administering a single intramuscular injection of hypertonic glycerol. Biochemical analyses included measurements of serum creatinine, urea, creatine kinase (CK), electrolytes, oxidative stress markers (glutathione peroxidase [GPX] and malondialdehyde [MDA]), and inflammatory cytokines (IL1 β , IL6, TNF- α). Kidney tissues were examined histologically to assess structural damage.

Results: The GLY-induced AKI group exhibited significantly elevated serum creatinine, urea, CK, proinflammatory cytokines, and MDA, alongside decreased GPX levels and substantial histopathologic damage. In contrast, the LQ treatment groups, especially at 50 mg/kg, showed significant reductions in serum creatinine, urea, CK levels, and inflammatory cytokines, with a notable improvement in GPX and a reduction in MDA levels. Electrolyte imbalances observed in the GLY group were also largely restored in the LQ-treated groups. Histopathological analysis revealed decreased tubular injury and overall tissue recovery in the LQ-treated groups.

Conclusions: LQ demonstrated significant nephroprotective effects in GLY-induced AKI, likely through attenuation of oxidative stress and inflammatory pathways. These findings position LQ as a promising therapeutic candidate for managing AKI, particularly in cases associated with RML, warranting further research on its clinical applicability in nephroprotection.

Keywords: myoglobin, CK, rhabdomyolysis, glycerol, AKI, liquiritigenin

Introduction

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a severe clinical condition characterized by a reversible abrupt reduction in kidney function within hours to days, manifested depending on an increment of at least 0.3mg/dL in serum creatinine level within 48 hours and/or decreased urine production (oliguria) during ≥ 6 hrs. This situation may be expanded for 7 days or less(1).

Previously, the expression "Acute renal failure" (ARF) demonstrated the clinical situation before it was modified into AKI(2). It affects mainly hospitalized patients, about 10-15% of total inpatients and 50% of critically ill patients(3). This intense syndrome causes a considerably high mortality rate. Although many medications were used to restore normal renal function, they negatively affected patients' economic situation(4). It causes up to 1.7 million yearly deaths(5).

AKI is attributed to various reasons, including dehydration, sepsis, medication toxicity, and internal substances, such as hemoglobin in cases of hemolysis and myoglobin (Mb) in cases of rhabdomyolysis (RML), which have potential nephrotoxicity for renal tubules, and underlying chronic conditions such as diabetes or hypertension(6). Due to its high prevalence and severe complications, such as cardiovascular disease (CVD), it is considered a critical health challenge that may develop into chronic kidney disease (CKD), especially in old-age patients and those with comorbidities like CVD and diabetes(2).

RML is one of the main contributors to AKI(7). It refers to the rapid breakdown of striated muscle and the diffusion of intracellular contents like creatinine kinase (CK), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), Mb, phosphates, and potassium (K⁺) into the blood circulation(8). RML is a multifactorial syndrome, including trauma caused by road traffic accidents, nephrotoxic drugs, poisonous materials, extensive muscle workouts, surgical operations, infectious disease, body temperature alteration, epilepsy, and genetic disorders(9). Biochemically, CK is considered a diagnostic criterion for RML and is highly increased, reaching more than fivefold the upper limit of the normal value or $>1,000$ U/L during 2-12 hrs. and peaking within 24-72 hrs., following the muscle injury. Serum CK concentration is believed to be a preferable predictor of AKI(10).

The prevalence of AKI provoked by RML is considerably high account, 19-58% of total RML cases, which account (10-40%) of total AKI cases. It is the leading cause of death among RML patients >50% of patients die due to renal injury(11). Several studies proposed that pathogenesis mechanisms of RML-mediated AKI are diverse, including 1-renal vasoconstriction due to hypovolemia and liberation of potent vasoconstrictors, 2-Mb-induced oxidative stress, as well as tubular cast formation 3-inflammation, and apoptosis, such as a study carried out by Hebert et al., 2022, they conclude that the release of vast amounts of potentially nephrotoxic materials, specifically Mb, and uric acid, leads to the development of AKI(12).

After muscle breakdown, serum Mb is markedly elevated, freely filtered by the glomerulus, reabsorbing and accumulating inside renal tubules, subsequently breaking down and releasing free iron (12, 13). Mb-ferrous (Fe²⁺) form, essential for oxygen-carrying, Fe²⁺ oxidized to ferric iron (Fe³⁺) by an oxidation reaction causes the liberation of hydroxyl radicals (OH[·]) (Fenton reaction) inside the tubular cell, Mb-derived Fe³⁺ tends to be more stable and converts via redox cycle to ferryl Mb (Mb-Fe⁴⁺), generating additional reactive metabolite and further precipitating oxidative stress causing peroxidation of the lipid membrane and cellular denaturation(14).

Oyagbemi et al. reported that inflammation is pivotal in developing AKI associated with RML. After muscle lysis and releasing toxic materials, which stimulate the production of proinflammatory mediators like IL1 β , IL6, and TNF- α , it results in intense RVR and ischemic injury. Mb precipitate in renal tubules activates the complement system, nuclear factor kappa beta (NF- κ β), Toll-like receptors (TLRs), which trigger cellular immunity, and Phagocytes. Inflammatory mediators like transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) and TNF- α , stimulated by these signaling pathways, lead to the maintenance of inflammation(15). Pro-inflammatory mediators like IL.1 β and IL6 are produced due to various harmful stimulations, such as infections and different forms of inflammation. These are

essential in stimulating and progressing inflammatory responses, encouraging the inflammatory acute phase, thereby promoting injured tissue repair(16). Mb-derived iron promotes oxidative stress by generating reactive species (ROS) that injure the tubular cell and stimulate the release of cytokines and chemokines, enhancing the leukocyte adhesion to the epithelial cell and necrosis of renal tubular cells(17).

It was reported that extract of the dried rhizomes of licorice is usually used for its life-enhancing attributes, the management of injuries or inflammatory disorders, and detoxification in traditional Chinese medicine, as well as widely used as food supplement products attributed mainly to flavonoids, the main active ingredients of licorice radix(18). Liquiritigenin (LQ) (7,4'-dihydroxy flavanone) is a dihydro flavonoid constituent derived from licorice radix, majorly from (*Glycyrrhiza urinalysis*) (19). It was approved that LQ has antioxidants, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferation, anti-tumor and antihyperlipidemic effects(20). Previous studies demonstrated the nephroprotective effects of LQ against cisplatin-mediated AKI through the recovery of mitochondrial damage of renal tubular epithelial cells via attenuating the ROS generation that mitigates oxidative stress(21). Moreover, LQ showed kidney protective effects against AKI mediated by intravenously administered folic acid by attenuating ferroptosis induced by iron aggregation(22).

In this study, we aim to assess the protective effects of the flavonoid LQ against AKI induced by GLY-mediated myoglobinuria in rabbits, examining its potential to mitigate renal damage through antioxidant and anti-inflammatory means.

. Materials and Methods

2.1 Animals

The study, conducted from December 2023 to July 2024, used sixty healthy male albino rabbits sourced from the Basra College of Medicine animal facility at Al-Basra University. The rabbits underwent a two-week acclimatization period before experimentation. This research followed the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals and was approved by the Animal Ethics Committee of the College of Medicine, Baghdad University. The rabbits, aged 6 months to 1 year and weighing 1-2 kg, were housed under controlled conditions of $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature, $50 \pm 5\%$ humidity, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. They were kept in five cages, with 12 rabbits per cage, and had free access to water and chewable food.

2.2 Experimental Design

These were followed by their division into five groups of 12 each. After 24 hrs. water deprivation, A single deep intramuscular (IM) injection of 8 ml/kg hypertonic glycerol(23), 50% v/v, divided into both rear limbs on the third day, was given to all the groups except the control group. The ISO was dissolved using the vehicle solution in (10: 15: 75) ratios of DMSO, Tween 80, and distilled water ratios. The groups were as follows:

- **Control Group:** Received 5 ml distilled water intraperitoneally (IP) without any glycerol treatment.
- **Induction Group (GLY):** A single IM injection of 8 ml/kg hypertonic glycerol solution (50%) was received on the third day.
- **Vehicle Group:** Administered the vehicle solution IP for five days, with a glycerol injection on the third day.
- **LO 30 Group:** Treated with 30 mg/kg LO IP for five days and received a glycerol injection on the third day.

- **LO 50 Group:** Treated with 50 mg/kg LO IP for five days and received a glycerol injection on the third day.

After 24 hours following the last dose, animals were anesthetized, and blood was collected for biochemical analyses. Kidneys were then harvested for histopathological examination.

2.3 Reagents and Materials

Liquiritigenin (purity $\geq 98\%$) was purchased from Chengdu Bio Purify Phytochemicals Ltd. Other reagents, including DMSO, Tween 80, and protease inhibitors, were sourced from Med Chem Express. ELISA kits were acquired from ELK Biotechnology Co. Ltd (Wuhan).

2.4 Serum Collection and Biochemical Analysis

Following the last administered dose, all rabbits were fasted for two hours before anesthesia. The euthanasia protocol included 35 mg/kg ketamine, 5 mg/kg xylazine hydrochloride, and 0.1 mg/kg acepromazine maleate (24). Approximately 3 ml of blood was drawn, allowed to clot for 15 minutes, and centrifuged at 4000 g for 10 minutes. The resulting serum was separated and stored in labeled Eppendorf tubes at -20°C for later biochemical analyses, including serum urea, creatinine, electrolytes (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+}), and creatine kinase (CK) levels as indicators of rhabdomyolysis and AKI.

2.5 Biochemical Markers Assessment

- **Renal Function Markers:** Serum urea and creatinine levels were measured using specific kits and the Mindray BS-240 clinical biochemistry analyzer, according to the manufacturer's instructions.
- **Serum Creatine Kinase (CK):** CK levels were assessed to indicate rhabdomyolysis using a specific kit according to the manufacturer's instructions. With the Mindray BS-240 analyzer.
- **Serum Electrolytes:** The concentrations of Sodium, potassium, and calcium were determined using dedicated kits and the Mindray BS-240 analyzer.

2.6 Kidney Tissue Collection and Preparation

After euthanasia, both kidneys were harvested, rinsed with normal saline to remove excess blood, decapsulated, and cross-sectioned. The left kidneys were preserved in 10% formalin for histopathological evaluation, while the right kidneys were placed in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and stored at -80°C for later preparation of tissue homogenates for oxidative stress and inflammatory marker analysis.

2.7 Preparation of Tissue Homogenates and Marker Analysis

Tissue homogenates were prepared from the right kidneys, which were thawed and washed with ice-cold PBS to remove clots. The tissues were minced into small pieces, weighed, and homogenized in fresh lysis buffer (PBS, pH 7.4) in a 1:9 w/v ratio (e.g., 100 mg of tissue with 900 μl lysis buffer) using a tissue homogenizer. The homogenates were centrifuged at 4°C at 10,000 g for 5 minutes. The supernatant was collected, divided into aliquots to prevent

repeated freeze-thaw cycles, and stored at $\leq -20^{\circ}\text{C}$ until inflammatory and oxidative marker assessments were conducted using ELISA.

2.8 Histopathological Examination of Kidney Tissues

The left kidneys preserved in formalin were sectioned into 5 μm slices, stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E), and prepared according to Bancroft's Manual of Histological Techniques(25). Histopathological changes were observed under a light microscope and evaluated based on interstitial vascular congestion, glomerular atrophy and congestion, interstitial inflammation, hyaline cast formation, acute tubular necrosis, and epithelial vacuolar degeneration.

2.9 Histopathological Scoring

A pathologist used a scoring system to evaluate renal tissue damage semi-quantitatively. Tissue damage was assessed in 10 fields per section per animal, and the average score for each group was calculated for comparison. The scoring system rated damage severity from 0 to 4 as follows: 0 (no change), 1 (1-25%), 2 (26-50%), 3 (51-75%), and 4 (>75%)(26)

Results

1. Effect of Liquiritigenin on Renal Function Biomarkers (Serum Creatinine and Urea)

In the induction group, serum urea and creatinine levels significantly increased ($p < 0.001$) compared to the control group, confirming renal dysfunction. The vehicle group showed no significant improvement in these markers. However, both LQ-treated groups (LQ30+GLY and LQ50+GLY) exhibited substantial reductions in serum urea and creatinine levels compared to the GLY-induced group ($p < 0.001$), with the LQ50+GLY group demonstrating the most pronounced protective effect (Figure 1).

Fig (1) effect of liquiritigenin on renal function Biomarkers (A) serum creatinine levels (B) serum urea levels statistically significant at *** $P < 0.001$ compared to control group, ### $P < 0.001$ compared with induction group, \$ $p < 0.05$, \$\$ $p < 0.01$, \$\$\$ $p < 0.001$ compared with LQ30 mg, control (healthy group), vehicle(solvent receivedgroup) ,LQ30(liquiritigenin 30 mg receivedgroup), LQ50(liquiritigenin 50 mg receivedgroup)

2-Effect of Liquiritigenin on Serum Creatine Kinase (CK) Levels

The GLY-induced group showed a significant elevation in CK levels ($p < 0.001$), indicating extensive muscle injury and successful induction of RML. The vehicle group did not show a significant difference in CK levels compared to the induction group. However, both LQ-treated groups displayed significant reductions in CK levels ($p < 0.01$), with no notable difference between the LQ30+GLY and LIQ50+GLY groups, suggesting LQ's role in mitigating RML-induced renal injury (Figure 2)..

Fig(2) Effect of LQ on serum CK level. statistically significant at *** $P < 0.001$ compared with control group, ### $P < 0.001$ compared with the induction group, \$ $p < 0.05$, \$\$ $p < 0.01$, \$\$\$ $p < 0.001$ compared with LQ30 mg., CK (creatinine kinase),control (healthy group), vehicle (solvent receivedgroup), LQ30(liquiritigenin 30 mg received group), LQ50(liquiritigenin 50 mg receivegroup)

3. Effect of Liquiritigenin on Electrolyte Imbalance

GLY-induced AKI led to significant electrolyte imbalances, with serum sodium (Na^+) and calcium (Ca^{2+}) levels significantly decreased ($p < 0.001$), while potassium (K^+) levels were significantly elevated ($p < 0.001$) compared to the control group. Both LQ30+GLY and LQ50+GLY groups showed improvements in electrolyte balance, with significant increases in Na^{2+} and Ca^{2+} levels and a significant decrease in K^+ levels compared to the GLY-induced group. The LQ50+GLY group showed the greatest effect in restoring electrolyte homeostasis (Figure 3).

Fig(3) Effect of Liquiritigenin on electrolyte imbalances (A) serum sodium levels, (B)serum potassium levels C- serum calcium levels, statistically significant at *** $P < 0.001$ compared to the control group, ### $P < 0.001$ compared to induction group, \$ $p < 0.05$, \$\$ $p < 0.01$, \$\$\$ $p < 0.001$ compared with LQ30 mg, control (healthy group), vehicle(solvent receivedgroup) ,LQ30(liquiritigenin 30 mg received group), LQ50(liquiritigenin 50 mg received group)

4-Effect of Liquiritigenin on Oxidative Stress Markers (GPX and MDA)

The induction group exhibited a marked decrease in the antioxidant enzyme GPX ($p < 0.001$) and an increase in the lipid peroxidation marker MDA ($p < 0.001$) relative to the control group, confirming high oxidative stress levels. Treatment with LQ significantly increased GPX levels and reduced MDA levels in both LQ30+GLY and LQ50+GLY groups, with the LQ50+GLY group displaying the most substantial effects. These results highlight LQ's ability to enhance antioxidant defenses and reduce oxidative damage in renal tissues (Figure 4).

Fig(4) Effect of liquiritigenin on tissue antioxidant /oxidant biomarkers, (A) GPX tissue levels, (B) MDA tissue levels. statistically significant at *** $P < 0.001$ compared to control group, ### $P < 0.001$ compared to induction group, \$ $p < 0.05$, \$\$ $p < 0.01$, \$\$\$ $p < 0.001$ compared with LQ30 mg, control (healthy group), vehicle(solvent receivedgroup) ,LQ30(liquiritigenin 30 mg received group), LQ50(liquiritigenin 50 mg received group)

5-Effect of Liquiritigenin on Proinflammatory Cytokines (IL6, TNF- α and IL1 β)

The induction showed significantly elevated proinflammatory cytokines IL6, TNF- α , and IL1 β ($p < 0.001$) compared to the control group, indicating an inflammatory response associated with AKI. The vehicle group showed no significant difference from the induction group. LQ30+GLY and LQ50+GLY groups exhibited a marked reduction in these cytokines compared to the GLY-induced group ($p < 0.001$), with the LQ50+GLY group showing a more significant reduction in IL6 and TNF- α levels. These findings suggest that LQ effectively modulates the inflammatory response in AKI (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Effects of liquiritigenin on renal tissue cytokines levels, (A)IL6, (B)TNF- α , (C)IL1 β significant at *** $P < 0.001$ compared with control group, ### $P < 0.001$ compared with induction group, \$ $p < 0.05$, \$\$ $p < 0.01$, \$\$\$ $p < 0.001$ compared with LQ30 mg, control (healthy group), vehicle(solvent receivedgroup),LQ30(liquiritigenin 30 mg received group), LQ50(liquiritigenin 50 mg received group).

6. Histopathological Analysis of Renal Tissue

Histopathological examination of renal tissues revealed significant structural damage in the GLY-induced AKI and Vehicle groups, while the LQ-treated groups demonstrated varying degrees of renal protection. The primary pathological features observed included tubular necrosis, glomerular congestion, interstitial inflammation, and hyaline cast formation, as summarized in Table 1 and illustrated in Figures (6). In the control group, the kidney appears within normal limits, this is indicated by the normal looking of glomeruli. Glomeruli in the cortex reveal typical architecture containing a normal Bowman's capsule, Bowman's space, and capillary tuft, Normal renal tubular epithelial cells from the sub-capsular area in the cortex to the medulla, tubular lumens of proximal convoluted tubules show protein content that usually appears with all renal sections figure 6(A-C); In the induction group, Glomeruli show variable degrees of atrophy (score 4). certain areas of the cortex show intensive interstitial inflammation (score 3). Renal tubular epithelium in the sub-capsular area reveals marked vacuolation (score 4), while other proximal and distal tubules in the cortex show hyaline degeneration (score 4) with marked protein cast (score 4). This group showed a significant difference from the control group ($p \leq 0.05$) Figure 6(D-F). Similar results were seen in the vehicle-treated group, where kidney sections showed marked vacuolation of renal tubular epithelium, glomerular atrophy, and renal vascular congestion Figure 6(G-I). This group shows no statistically significant differences from the induction group ($P \geq 0.05$).

Marked improvement of renal changes was seen in the LQ (30 mg), in which this group showed significant ($p \leq 0.05$) differences regarding all study parameters compared to the induction group figures 6(J-L). Superior renal improvements were obtained in the liquiritigenin (50 mg) treated group in Figure 6(M-O). This group showed a marked reduction in all changes seen in the other groups. The kidney showed marked restoration of renal structural normalcy, in which this group had no statistical differences from the control group except for the hyaline cast. In comparison with induction, liquiritigenin (50 mg) showed significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) in the improvement of renal function. All of the said parameters were scored. All scoring parameters are shown in the table (1).

Table 1: The averages of histopathological changes of kidney in all study groups with scoring percentage

Pathological changes	Cont. % (score)	Veh. % (score)	IND. % (score)	LQ 30 % (score)	LQ 50 % (score)
Inflammation	0 (0)	69±3.41 B (3)	62±1.45B (3)	62±1.45B (3)	0 A (0)
Glomerular atrophy	0 (0)	81±0.15 B (4)	77±0.93B (4)	14±1.22 D (1)	0 A (0)
Glomerular congestion	0 (0)	93±0.09 B (4)	81±2.4 B (4)	30±2.39 C (2)	0 A (0)
Epithelial hyaline degeneration	0 (0)	89±4.63 B (4)	93±3.1 B (4)	26±0.89 D (2)	9±1.62 A (1)
Epithelial vacuolar degeneration	0 (0)	82±2.77 B (4)	82±1.11 B (4)	29±3.74 D (2)	4±1.51 A (1)
Hyaline cast formation	0 (0)	91±0.4 B (4)	95±0.83 B (4)	26±0.8 D (2)	27±0.2 D (2)
Interstitial vascular congestion	0 (0)	65±5.54B (4)	69 ±4.12B (3)	5±3.3 A (1)	0 A (0)

- The values in the table expressed as a mean ± standard error (SE). cont.: control group, Veh: vehicle group, IND: glycerol group, LQ30mg: liquiritigenin group 30 mg dose, LQ 50: liquiritigenin group dose 50 mg.

Capital letters refer to significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between numbers in the rows.

Figure 6: Histopathological findings in the study groups. The kidney section of the control group shows A: normal glomeruli (black arrow) and normal proximal (blue arrow) and distal (green arrow), B: control group shows normal subcapsular renal tubules (black arrow), C: shows normal proximal renal tubular epithelium (black arrow), normal interstitial capillaries (blue arrow), D: induction group shows glomerular atrophy (black arrow), hyaline degeneration of renal tubules (red arrow), protein cast (green arrow) in the cortical renal tubules and interstitial inflammation (yellow arrow) E: shows marked vacuolation of renal tubular epithelium of the sub-capsular region (black arrow) F: shows marked vacuolation of renal tubular (black arrow), hyaline degeneration of cortical renal tubules (red arrow) and protein cast in both proximal (green arrow) and distal (yellow arrow) renal tubules. G: The kidney section of the vehicle group shows glomerular atrophy (black arrows): The kidney section of the vehicle group shows marked vacuolation of renal tubular epithelium in the sub-capsular region (black arrow). H: vehicle group shows renal vascular congestion (black arrow) I: LQ30 shows interstitial inflammation (black arrow). J: kidney section of the LQ (30 mg) treated group shows some atrophic glomeruli (black arrow) vacuolation of renal tubular epithelium in all proximal (blue arrow) and distal (green arrow) tubules in the cortex, with mild protein aggregates in the renal tubules (yellow arrow) K: LQ30 shows glomerular congestion (black arrow) vacuolation of renal tubular epithelium in all proximal (blue arrow) and distal (green arrow) tubules in the cortex, with mild protein aggregates in the renal tubules (yellow arrow) L: group shows vacuolation of medullary renal tubular epithelium (blue arrow), with protein cast in the renal tubules (yellow arrow). M: The kidney section of the liquiritigenin (50 mg) treated group shows normal glomeruli (black arrow) and normal proximal (blue arrow) and distal (green arrow) renal tubules. N: The kidney section of the LQ (50 mg) treated group shows normal subcapsular renal tubular epithelium (black arrow) in the cortex. O: LQ50 shows normal glomerulus (black arrow) and mild hyaline degeneration of the proximal (blue arrow) tubules.

Discussion

Phytomedicines are efficient, stunning products with global attentiveness in consideration of their therapeutic effects, widely available sources, and affordable cost compared with chemical medicines(27). Polyphenols, specifically flavonoids, are widely investigated in several studies using the glycerol model to induce myoglobinuric-AKI due to their anti-inflammatory antioxidant and antiapoptotic properties(28) GLY-induced myoglobinuric-AKI is the most frequently used model to study AKI and predict a novel treatment since it shows a remarkable similarity of renal failure induced by myoglobinuria in humans due to traumatic injury or extensive muscle workouts(29).

Renal vasoconstriction, ischemic- injury, tubular occlusion due to Mb cast formation, and Mb-induced oxidative stress are the primary pathological mechanisms of GLY-induced AKI. Vasoconstriction, a characteristic feature of AKI evoked by GLY, is mediated by the release of several vasoconstrictors, including (Ang, vasopressin, MDA, endothelin, and TNF- α), due to reduced intravascular fluids after diffusion into ruptured muscles, Mb nephrotoxicity, and inflammation, consequently ischemic injury and reduces GFR. At this time, vasoconstriction decreases the tubular fluids, which is considered a proper medium for Mb cast formation, causing tubular occlusion and aggravating the reduction in the GFR(30). The previous factors, plus structural damage of kidney tissues, such as diminishing brush borders and tubular necrosis, lead to the impairment of kidney excretory function, causing the accumulation of nitrogenous waste products(31). Additionally, elevation in serum creatinine is attributed to RML as injured muscle releases a vast amount of creatinine(32). Our results exhibited a marked elevation in renal function biomarkers (Ur and Cr), in addition to CK levels, in the induction group, which confirms the induction of RML and subsequent AKI incidence because the significant elevation in serum CK, an indicator of RML, meanwhile, elevation in urea and creatinine levels reflect a primary manifestation of AKI(33). supported by GLY mediated histopathological alteration in renal tissues, including tubular necrosis, hyalin degeneration, tubular cast formation, and glomerular atrophy.

The earlier results align with the current study's findings, which reported similar biochemical and histopathological changes after administering the GLY solution(23). The vehicle-treated group didn't produce any significant changes compared with the induction group, which was attributed to the absence of protective effects of the vehicle Solution. In contrast, LQ-treated groups showed a significant reduction in renal function parameters (Ur and Cr) and CK level, compared with the induction group, as well as attenuation of histological changes, as the LQ-treated groups significantly improved the structural changes presented in the GLY group, suggesting possible renoprotective effects, mitigated GLY-mediated AKI as well as attenuating the RML progressing. LQ in a previous study showed a remarkable reduction in both Ur and Cr Levels in the cisplatin-induced AKI model, which supports our findings(21).

The current study's results were compatible with those of Yosef et al. They reported that Licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) extract exhibited nephroprotective activity against gentamicin-induced nephrotoxicity. The results showed its ability to improve renal function by a significant reduction of Ur and Cr(34). Nissan et al., 2022 reported the nephroprotective effect of *G. glabra* against gentamicin-induced renal damage via inhibiting proinflammatory mediators and enhancing antioxidant enzymes, scavenging ROS, and restoring normal renal function(35). the ability of LQ to restore normal renal function may be explained by its blocking effect against the angiotensin enzyme, which in turn blocks angiotensin-mediated renal vasoconstriction(36). In addition to LQ's free radical scavenging properties, they inhibit lipid peroxidation of renal tubular cells and the formation of potent vasoconstrictors like MDA and isoprostane F₂, which enhance renal blood flow(37). Evidence also supports the vasodilatory effects of LQ via the enhancement of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP), which may modulate renal vasoconstriction(38).

AKI causes a disturbance in the water and electrolyte homeostasis related to a reduction in GFR (39). The present study's findings revealed a significant decrease in serum Na⁺ level in the induction and vehicle groups that received GLY, compared with the control group, attributed to tubular damage leading to reabsorption impairment.

Our results are in agreement with the findings of previous studies that exhibited a significant reduction in serum Na⁺ level in the rats model of GLY-induced RML and an increase in fractional Na⁺ excretion (17, 40). Contrary to our findings, many studies reported a significant increase in serum Na⁺ level after GLY administration, which may be attributed to hypovolemia and the hypertonicity of the GLY solution, in addition to fluid restriction as a compensatory renal mechanism to overcome hypovolemia. This also may be attributed to ATN, which results in a decline in the kidney's functional units. This action will stimulate the multiple compensatory mechanisms in the hyper-functioning remaining nephrons, most notably the augmented rates of Na⁺ reabsorption that lead to hypernatremia. (41, 42).

The LQ (30,50) treatment groups reveal a significant increase in Na⁺ levels, the highest improvement seen with the LQ 50 mg dose. The LQ (30,50) treatment groups significantly reduced K⁺ levels, reflecting the LQ renoprotective effects. On the other hand, GLY administration exhibited a marked increase in serum K⁺ in the induction and vehicle groups. The previous studies showed elevated serum K⁺ levels in the animals that received GLY injections, which is consistent with our findings. (11, 43). Due to muscle breakdown, Hyperkalemia usually manifests as electrolyte disturbances associated with RML. Hyperkalemia may cause severe cardiac complications, specifically arrhythmia, that must be managed as soon as possible (43). Hyperkalemia is also attributed to reduced urine output, decreasing K⁺ excretion (44). The ability of LQ to reverse Na⁺ and K⁺ levels may be attributed to the mineralocorticoid action of licorice active constituent, which preserves sodium and water and releases potassium in the urine, which may help reverse the hyperkalemia and hyponatremia associated with RML (37, 45). Moreover, Studies have demonstrated that flavonoids could effectively ameliorate electrolyte disturbances associated with GLY-induced AKI (46). In addition, the ability of LQ to retrieve normal kidney function can reverse the electrolyte disturbances as it enhances the filtration and reabsorption mechanisms. At the same time, Ca²⁺ levels in the induction and vehicle groups significantly decreased with no significant changes between the two groups, which is consistent with the findings of earlier investigators. This hypocalcemia is attributed to the trapping of calcium intracellularly in the early stage of AKI (oliguric phase); studies have shown that hypocalcemia is temporary at the beginning stage of RML, as the Ca²⁺ diffused after muscle breakdown, which may result in hypercalcemia (47). LQ treatment groups reversed the hypocalcemia seen in the induction group significantly.

Numerous investigators have mentioned the role of inflammation and oxidative stress in the pathogenesis of GLY-induced AKI. These studies reported that pro-inflammatory cytokines and ROS significantly initiate and develop AKI due to the Mb nephrotoxic effects. Accordingly, inflammation and oxidative stress are considered the primary therapeutic targets in the earlier studies to manage AKI stimulated by GLY. (11). In this study, renal tissue oxidative stress markers (MDA, GPX) showed significant changes compared with the control group; MDA was significantly high, while GPX was significantly low, reflecting that oxidative stress causes lipid peroxidation and depletion of antioxidant enzymes. These results were compatible with previous research, which reported comparable results regarding oxidative stress markers (42, 48). The treatment group showed significant changes in these markers, as LQ reduced tissue MDA level and elevated tissue GPX compared with the induction group and in a dose-dependent manner. Previously, LQ exhibited the same results in modulating oxidative stress markers against liver damage triggered by arsenic trioxide (49). Several factors generated ROS, producing oxidative stress like muscle disintegration-induced systemic inflammation, ischemic reperfusion injury, and myoglobin-derived free iron. Updated evidence reported the role of iron overload in GLY-AKI through ferroptosis, a different form of tubular epithelial cell death due to iron trapping-mediated lipid peroxidation (50). Advanced evidence suggested that LQ could mitigate AKI by inhibiting ferroptosis through VKORC1 action and reducing oxidative stress markers; therefore, the reduced MDA level by LQ could be related to this effect, which supports our results (22). Moreover, polyphenols, particularly flavonoids, have astonishing free radicals scavenging properties through electron donation or hydrogen atom transfer, making radical species more stable and chelating effects that could alleviate iron-derived ROS (48). Several signaling pathways regulate ROS generation and subsequent oxidative stress in AKI.

The nuclear factor erythroid-2-related factor 2 (Nrf2), which is a transcription factor with high value in the regulation of antioxidant enzymes involved in the restoration of redox balance during stress conditions (51) It was

reported that LQ stimulates this factor, which in turn replenishes the tissue content of various antioxidant enzymes, including GPX, that attenuate oxidative stress and prevent cellular damage (52). In response to various harmful excitors like trauma and toxic damage, inflammation develops through releasing of several pro-inflammatory mediators and may lead to severe complications particularly in acute cases response (53). The pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL1 β , IL6, TNF- α) are the central cytokines involved in the pathogenesis of AKI induced by GLY, stimulating inflammation and exacerbating AKI by inducing cellular damage and promoting leukocyte infiltration, oxidative stress generation further exacerbates inflammation, thereby intensifying renal injury. In the current study, cytokines (IL1 β , IL6, and TNF- α) were markedly elevated in the induction group, highlighting an inflammatory response associated with AKI; these findings were in line with the earlier research showed an elevation in renal tissue levels of these cytokines (27, 47, 54). vehicle group showed no significant change compared with the induction group, reflecting that solvent has no effects on inflammatory markers. At the same time, LQ treatment groups exhibited a significant reduction in all inflammatory markers in a dose-dependent manner, except for IL1 β , which showed no significant difference between the two doses. Cytokines associated with RML are released in response to various stimuli, including oxidative stress that induces T-lymphocytes and macrophages, muscle damage, myoglobinuria, and ischemic injury (55).

Studies mentioned the significant role of TNF- α in GLY-induced AKI pathogenesis; it is stimulated rapidly after GLY administration, induces immune cell infiltration, traps neutrophils, and aggravates the secretion of other cytokines. The released TNF- α can amplify inflammatory response through its activation impact on nuclear factor kappa b (NF- κ B). This factor regulates the expression of several pro-inflammatory cytokines; consequently, its activation leads to transcribing stimulation of its downstream cytokines (IL6, IL1 β , TNF- α). Evidence has shown that mitigating TNF- α can protect against GLY-AKI (47, 56). In addition, oxidative stress, evoked by Mb and other toxic materials released from damaged muscles, stimulates NF- κ B, thereby enhancing the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (30). Similarly, studies mentioned the pivotal impact of (IL1 β and IL6) in the development of AKI due to GLY administration, which is released in response to inflammation of renal tissues and infiltrated immune cells. It has been shown that IL6 serum levels directly reflect the severity of renal damage (57, 58).

It has been reported in several previous studies the inflammatory suppression action of LQ and licorice-active constituents through suppression of the NF- κ B signaling pathway that inhibits cytokines production such as TNF- α and IL6. (38, 59). Moreover, evidence supports the anti-inflammatory role of LQ in modulating the cytokines induced by lipopolysaccharides' effects on microglial cells and in the hydrogen peroxide-exposed mouse (60). In addition, LQ can mitigate inflammation-induced cartilage damage in rats by inhibiting TNF- α and IL1 β (61). LQ mitigated the pro-inflammatory cytokines involved in the pathogenesis of diabetic nephropathy by suppressing NF- κ B and nod-like protein 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome pathway (62). Furthermore, oxidative stress and inflammation are interchangeable; they stimulate each other. LQ's previously mentioned antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects, by suppressing gene expression of IL1 β , IL6, and TNF- α , can inhibit this vicious circle (63). Therefore, inhibiting of NF- κ B, NLRP3, and antioxidant effects of LQ could be explain the pro-inflammatory markers reduction, in the current study. Histopathological evaluations provided concrete evidence of the structural preservation afforded by LQ. In the GLY-induced AKI and vehicle groups, severe tubular necrosis, glomerular atrophy, and interstitial inflammation were observed, reflecting profound renal damage. LQ treatment, especially at the 50 mg/kg dose, minimized these histological alterations, as evidenced by minimal necrosis, preserved glomerular structure, and reduced inflammation. These findings underscore LQ's potential to prevent myoglobin-induced oxidative stress, limit leukocyte infiltration, and mitigate structural degradation in renal tissue. Similar nephroprotective agents, such as magnesium isoglycyrrhizinate, an active constituent of licorice roots, have demonstrated comparable effects, reducing renal injury by lowering ROS production and dampening inflammatory responses (64).

Conclusion

This work confirms in vitro the high nephroprotective activity of Liquiritigenin against glycerol-induced AKI in rabbits. Our data indicate that LQ, at the higher dosage of 50 mg/kg, significantly reduced renal dysfunction, oxidative stress, and inflammation, which are key actors in AKI pathophysiology, especially in those forms related to RML. The marked reduction of serum biomarkers, proinflammatory cytokines, and oxidative stress markers, along with notable improvements in renal tissue architecture, underlines the potential of LQ as a therapeutic agent.

Male rabbits used in this experiment gave a far better reflection of the human AKI response and were essential for elucidating LQ's protective mechanisms and long-term impact on renal health. Characterized by anti-inflammatory and antioxidant characteristics judged by cytokine and oxidative markers changes, LQ may be one of the most promising and effective alternatives to conventional AKI treatments, especially for managing AKI associated with muscle injury and myoglobinuria.

In summary, Liquiritigenin is a promising agent for preventing kidney injury. Future studies are necessary to elucidate its molecular mechanisms, perform a detailed assessment of its safety profile, and consider clinical applications for AKI management. The study lays the foundation for the furtherance of LQ toward its potential therapeutic application in the prevention and mitigation of renal damage in patients with AKI, especially those at high risk of RML-induced kidney injury.

Study Limitations

- 1. Species-Specific Differences:** Male rabbits were selected for their physiological similarities to humans regarding kidney structure and injury response. However, inherent differences may affect the translatability of Liquiritigenin's (LQ) nephroprotective effects on human AKI cases. Further studies, particularly in human renal tissue models or clinical trials, are needed to confirm the relevance of these findings in human patients.
- 2. Single AKI Model:** This study utilized a glycerol-induced AKI model, mainly mimicking rhabdomyolysis-associated AKI. While LQ demonstrated efficacy in this context, its effectiveness in other forms of AKI, such as those caused by sepsis, ischemia-reperfusion, or nephrotoxic drugs, remains unknown. Testing LQ in various AKI models could provide a more comprehensive understanding of its potential as a general nephroprotective agent.
- 3. Limited Dose Range:** The study investigated only two doses of LQ (30 mg/kg and 50 mg/kg), which may not fully represent the optimal therapeutic range for maximum efficacy and safety. Expanding the study to include a wider range of doses would help determine the minimum effective dose and evaluate any possible toxicity at higher levels, aiding in the establishment of a safer dosing profile for future applications.

Ethical Approval

All animal procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals and were approved by the Animal Ethics Committee of the College of Medicine, Baghdad University (Approval No. [insert approval number if available]). The study adhered to internationally accepted standards for laboratory animal care and welfare.

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Data Availability

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration

The authors declare that they have no competing interests related to this study.

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